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ABSTRACT

The article deals with active scientific activity of the literary scholar and translator Leo Kossuth from Berlin. For many years he has been studying Kazakh literature in Germany, is the author of prefaces to the books by Kazakh writers published in Germany, and publishes reviews of these books in newspapers and magazines. He has published the books “Volk & Welt. Autobiographisches Zeugnis von einem legendären Verlag”, “Der Hut flog mir vom Kopfe. Majakowskis Zylinder?” and poetry collection “Abai. Zwanzig Gedichte” with his translation of Abai Kunanbayev’s poetry into German.

Keywords: literary criticism, analysis, research, review, article, translation.

German literary scholar, translator Leo Kossuth can be considered one of the most active representatives of the modern German school of literary criticism. He is one of the best specialists in Germany on literature of Russia and the CIS republics. Among the objects of his research is Kazakh literature. In the XX century, he worked for more than thirty years in the publishing house “Volk und Welt”, which published books of national literatures of the USSR. Before its dissolution (in 2001), the “Volk und Welt” publishing house managed to publish books from 23 national literatures of the USSR in German, including independent publications by 98 authors, including S. Yesenin, V. Mayakovsky, M. Bulgakov, I. Ilf and E. Petrov, M. Zoshchenko, M. Tsvetaeva, E. Yevtushenko, A. Voznesensky, B. Okudzhava, V. Rasputin, A. Grin, V. Dudintsev, A. Tarkovsky, V. Shukshin, A. Kim, T. Tolstaya, L. Ulitskaya, V. Pelevin and others. From Kazakh literature, books by Mukhtar Auezov, Takhavi Akhtanov, Anuar Alimzhanov, Abish Kekilbayev, Satimzhan Sanbayev, Olzhas Suleimenov, Dukenbay Doszhanov were published. In some of these books, he was the author of prefaces or afterwords. In Germany, for many years he published reviews of the works by Kazakh authors in newspapers and magazines.

The poetry collection of the famous Kazakh poet O. Suleimenov “In Azimut der Nomaden”, published in Berlin in 1981, included the afterword by L. Kossuth. In it, the German literary scholar presented a detailed literary analysis of the most famous poetic works of the Kazakh poet, included into this collection. The author begins his analysis by examining the poem “Earth, Bow Down to Man”, excerpts from which are given in the book. Assessing the significance of this work, he characterizes it as follows: “Suleimenov tries to give his own concepts of universal scale to such a great event as the beginning of the conquest of space, calling this event the “Second Great Age”, depicting it not in detail, but generalizing it in the prism of art – historical, social and philosophical generalization; while acting not abstractly, but involving the experience of mankind in spatial and temporal dimensions of a new, cosmic vision” [1, p. 195]. L. Kossuth explains that the name of spaceship “Vostok” becomes central metaphor of the poem. This name is symbolic, as it denotes Central Asia, “where over the centuries the fundamental changes have taken place” [1, p. 196]. L. Kossuth

points out the presence in the poem of a wide variety of associations connected with the word “Vostok”.

Introducing the poem “Clay Book” by O. Suleimenov to German readers, L. Kossuth briefly outlines its content and proceeds to analyze the poem, or rather, the part of it that is included into this collection. Urging German readers to follow the Kazakh poet’s symbolic elements of his poetry, L. Kossuth shares the author’s interpretation of history of the Scythian conquerors and their traditions. However, along with this, the German literary scholar also notes the modernity of the poem which is being interpreted. An interesting fact of L. Kossuth’s literary analysis is his recognition of a certain complexity in perceiving the works of the Kazakh poet. As the German literary scholar rightly noted, “a certain complexity in reading Suleimenov is a complexity that conceals the joy of knowledge”. This remark seems to us to be a code for defining the features of the entire foreign perception of O. Suleimenov’s work, which marked a new stage in the international reception of modern Kazakh literature. In general, the informative multi-page afterword by L. Kossuth presented a thorough literary analysis of O. Suleimenov’s creativity to German readers, demonstrated artistic and aesthetic features, motives and images, genre, compositional and stylistic nuances, and evolution of the Kazakh poet’s creativity. This publication was important document that revealed certain patterns and trends in reception of the Kazakh poet’s creativity in Germany.

The next example of the active scientific activity of the German literary scholar L. Kossuth can be the review “Informative and interesting” in the newspaper “Berliner Zeitung” (1981). In it, he highly appreciates the novel “Minaret, or the End of a Legend” by the Kazakh writer Abish Kekilbayev. L. Kossuth notes that “Kekilbayev offers the readers to experience great intellectual pleasure, giving them the opportunity to participate in a very intense process of solving complex situations and events occurring in the conditions of the Central Asian feudal society” [2]. The author of the article emphasizes that composition of the novel is based on psychological revealing of the characters, thanks to which Kekilbayev acquaints the readers with Eastern mentality.

It is also worth mentioning the review “A Millennium as a Day in Life” [3] in the “Berliner Zeitung” on the book of novellas by Satimzhan Sanbayev “When

They Yearn for a Myth”, published by the publishing house “Volk und Welt” in 1976.

During the period of Kazakhstan’s independence, L. Kossuth continued his active work on the research and popularization of Kazakh literature in Germany. Thanks to his efforts and with the assistance of the Embassy of Kazakhstan in Germany, the publication of the “Kazakhstan Library” in German began. The first Kazakh author in this project was Abdizhamil Nurpeisov. In October 2006, the presentation of the novel “The Last Duty” by Abdizhamil Nurpeisov was successfully held in Berlin, Hamburg, and Munich. The translation was done by Annelore Nitschke. She as a brilliant translator, was attracted by L. Kossuth to this work. In addition, it was he who contributed to the publication of the work when, together with A. Nurpeisov, he visited the publisher Dagieli in Frankfurt am Main, who agreed to publish the novel “The Last Duty”. This event is significant, as it opens the “Kazakhstan Library” in Germany. Moreover, already the following month, within the framework of the “Kazakhstan Library” project, Abish Kekilbayev’s novel “Minaret, or the End of a Legend” was re-published. At the presentation of this book in Berlin, L. Kossuth spoke about the creativity of the Kazakh writer, with whom he has been closely collaborating for a long time.

L. Kossuth publishes reviews and articles about the literature of Kazakhstan in German magazines. In particular, in 2002, his article about the novel by Abdizhamil Nurpeisov “The Last Duty” appeared in the German magazine “Ossietzky”, and in 2003, the same magazine published a review of the novel by the Kazakh writer Gerold Belger “The House of the Wanderer”. In the article “When the Sea Disappears”, he openly called for the publication of the novel “The Last Duty” by A. Nurpeisov in Germany: “If our society were not so oriented towards the West, then the novel “The Last Duty”, the author of which is the Kazakh Abdizhamil Nurpeisov, would have been translated into German long ago and would have been evaluated as a great work of the world literature” [4]. This review of the novel “The Last Duty” played important role in the appearance of its German edition.

L. Kossuth has visited Kazakhstan many times. During his stay in Almaty in 2003, he presented the Department of World Literature and International Relations of the M.O. Auezov Institute of Literature and Art of the Academy of Sciences of Kazakhstan with his book dedicated to the history of the publishing house “Volk und Welt”. The book was published in 2002 in Berlin. It consists of 37 chapters, one of which is dedicated to Kazakhstan. In this chapter, the author talks about his meetings with famous Kazakh writers and poets, and about German publications of literature from Kazakhstan. Thus, recalling one of the trips to Almaty with the editors of the publishing house, L. Kossuth writes: “The editorial board was astonished by the fact that history of Kazakhstan was studied through the Kazakh literature, which in many ways did not have written monuments, and allowed us to become familiar with the basis of the national identity of the Kazakhs” [5, pp. 137-138].

In the book “Volk&Welt. Autobiographisches Zeugnis von einem legendären Verlag» in the chapter

on Kazakhstan, the author also writes about how in 1973 he and his wife Charlotte spent two weeks on Kazakh land. Together with the writers A. Nurpeisov, T. Akhtanov, A. Kekilbayev, they lived in the steppe, in a large yurt. An interesting fact was that a Kazakh girl was named after L. Kossuth’s wife – Charlotte. Sixteen years later, the Kazakh Charlotte was invited with her parents to visit Berlin [5, p. 137].

One of the articles in the book was written by the author under the impression of a significant event in cultural life of Kazakhstan – on February 18, 2000, one of the streets in Berlin was renamed “Abaj Strasse”. L. Kossuth writes: “Abai, after whom the street in Berlin is named, is sometimes called the “Kazakh Goethe”. This metaphor has a ground, as it implies the significance of this poet, composer and educator for national literature, the universality of his creativity and activities” [5, p. 43].

In 2007, the publishing house “Oenel” in Cologne published the book “Abai. Zwanzig Gedichte” (“Abai. Twenty Poems”), which included Abai’s poems translated by L. Kossuth. The publication of this book can be called a significant event in the international popularization of Abai Kunanbayev’s creativity, since the translation is of high quality.

In the process of translating the poems of the Kazakh poet Abai Kunanbayev, L. Kossuth repeatedly sought advice from G. Belger, who knows German, Russian, and Kazakh. The translation of Abai’s poems into German was highly appreciated by him. The book was published in three languages: Kazakh, German, and Russian. It also included L. Kossuth’s article “My Path to Abai and Issues of Translating His Poems” in which the author talked about how the process of translating Abai’s poems into German went on. He writes that Abai impressed him with his demanding attitude towards himself, when he looks back on his life, when he realizes himself as a fighter, regretting that he does not have enough strength to fight, and presents a report to his contemporaries. The German translator, trying to understand the experiences of the Kazakh poet, asks: “Perhaps he looked with such sadness at what he had achieved from the position of the rest of his life?” [6]. He further writes: “his entire poem, his style, the sustained dynamics from line to line, I should not lose sight of all this when expressing my attitude towards Abai” [6].

The author of the article also tells about how the novel “The Path of Abai” by M.O. Auezov was published by the publishing house “Kultur und Fortschritt”, where he worked as the editor-in-chief of the publishing house for publication of the Soviet authors. According to L. Kossuth, it is unlikely that anyone who read the novel by M.O. Auezov dedicated to Abai will forget it. The German author became acquainted with the image of Abai thanks to the art, strength, and style of presentation of M.O. Auezov. L. Kossuth believes that one of the important incentives for him to reproduce Abai in German was the opening of Abai Street in Berlin.

From this article, one can learn how the German literary scholar perceives the Kazakh poet, what impresses him and what he admires: “I understood almost intuitively: biblical and creative power of Abai’s

words, which are original, irreplaceable, full of deep meaning and sense, and also break the traditions that have become routine, right down to versification, metaphor, intonation, poses complex national problems for the poet-translator, not to mention the attitude to religion. The immortality of Abai's poems, which is present in everything that concerns the poet's personality, his life experience should be also added to this" [6].

In conclusion of the article, L. Kossuth sums up: "Twenty poems is a small number of selected ones, and yet, summing up, I would say: What a magnificent poet speaks with these verses! How he captivates, tormented by his philosophical struggle to comprehend the irreconcilable and inseparable opposition of mortality and immortality!" [6].

The mastery of L. Kossuth, who felt Abai's poetic reflections with all his heart and soul, commands respect; one can feel how carefully he chose every word, trying to accurately convey all the national shades of Abai's poetry.

This book continued the release of the "Kasachische Bibliothek" series. Germany is one of the countries that have shown interest in Kazakh literature during the period of independence. This is proven by the appearance of this series of books, which includes the works of many Kazakh authors. In addition to the above-mentioned published works by A. Nurpeisov and A. Kekilbayev, in 2008 the novel "Blizzard" by Takhaui Akhtanov was published, in 2009 the presentation of Gerold Belger's novel "The House of the Wanderer" in the translation of Christina Lichtenfeld took place. In 2009, Olzhas Suleimenov's poetry collection "A Minute of Silence at the Edge of the World" and Gerold Belger's novel "The House of the Wanderer" were published, translated by Christina Lichtenfeld. In 2011, Ilyas Yesenberlin's book "Nomads. The Last Hour", translated by Simone Pel, was published. In 2013, Dukenbay Doszhanov's book "The Silk Road", translated by Ruprecht Vilnov, was published. In 2014, Mukagali Makatayev's collection "The Mountains Are a Legend" was published.

It should be noted that L. Kossuth has experience in translating poetry. In particular, he translated poems

by M. Lermontov and S. Yesenin, and at the beginning of his career he was preparing a dissertation "Mayakovsky's Creativity in Germany". Then L. Kossuth published the creative heritage of Vladimir Mayakovsky in five volumes, accompanying them with introductory articles. In 2013, he published the book "Der Hut flog mir vom Kopfe. Mayakowskys Zylinder?", which included his dissertation on the creativity of V. Mayakovsky in Germany and correspondence with German writers, poets, essayists on the creativity of the Russian poet.

L. Kossuth can rightfully be called an active representative of the modern German school of literary criticism. In his scientific articles devoted to Kazakh literature, he demonstrated excellent knowledge of the history of Kazakh literature and its most prominent representatives. L. Kossuth was personally acquainted with many Kazakh writers and poets; he made a great contribution to the development of Kazakh-German literary relations. In 2003, he was awarded the Prize of the Kazakhstan representative office of the International PEN Club for active popularization of Kazakh literature in Germany.

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